

Research Data Systems Strategy 2025-30

Acknowledgment of Country

AuScope Acknowledges the Traditional Custodians and first Earth scientists of the lands, waterways and skies across the Australian continent, including where our team lives, learns and creates data on Country¹.

We admire their long and continuing connection to Country over tens of thousands of years. We are grateful to walk alongside the longest, continuous living cultures in the world. In the spirit of Reconciliation, and towards equity in Earth systems, we seek to build relationships with Indigenous scientists and communities and centre their approaches to - and knowledges in - our work. We pay our deepest respects to all Aboriginal and/or Torres Strait Islander Elders, past and present.

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Photo by Will Turner via Unsplash

Pictured (left): Beautiful Gadigal Country photographed from Sky Country, where Land and Sea Country meet.

Pictured (covers): A rock outcrop on Boon Wurrung Country with a semi-transparent data visualisation overlay. Images by Iliya Jokic and Conny Schneider, respectively, via Unsplash.

1. Common Ground (2021): <https://bit.ly/3F7tSYR>

Introduction

This strategy aims to help the AuScope team design and deliver research data systems that are ready for future research challenges.

Executive summary

This document outlines the AuScope Research Data Systems Strategy 2025-30 (Strategy). It indicates current activities that align with this Strategy and highlights how resources should be allocated to ensure AuScope's research data, data products, and software systems are:

- Designed, developed, managed, maintained and used to ensure data, data products and software across all processing levels are aligned with the FAIR¹, CARE² and open science principles;
- Operated and governed by international best practices and agreed discipline and technical standards; and
- Recognised by relevant external parties through leadership, development and collaborative problem-solving.

AuScope's Research Data Systems portfolio provides strategic and operational support to strengthen these claims by responding to the distinct requirements and capabilities of AuScope's Programs, Projects and communities.

Background

AuScope's Vision is to help enable a sustainable and resilient nation through predictive geoscience. Its Mission is to build an integrated and collaborative research platform that services and facilitates theoretical and applied geoscientific research. AuScope's Vision, Mission, and seven Goals are articulated in the AuScope 10-Year Strategy 2020-2030 (Organisational Strategy)³. AuScope supported Projects, instruments, engagements and activities are expected to align with this Organisational Strategy and resourced accordingly.

In explicit acknowledgement of the importance of research data, Goal 2 of the Organisational Strategy is to develop capacity for predictive geoscience by applying global data principles and data management best practices. It references the challenges of supporting the diverse, complex, and evolving data landscape of geoscience research and includes the analytical, observational, and computational methods that produce subdiscipline-specific challenges.

Since the launch of the Organisational Strategy in 2020, there have been ongoing developments, shifts and disruptions, as is expected within any research domain. For example, the growth in artificial intelligence (AI), including natural language processing (NLP), machine learning (ML), and computer vision, has led to direct applications within the geosciences. This Strategy focuses on supporting data, data products and software with a strong and agile foundational capability, ensuring we can adapt to future advances.

With the vision to provide foundational data products and services for the Australian geoscience research community, this Strategy builds on the principles of research integrity and scientific excellence as outlined in the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science (2021)⁴. It acknowledges AuScope's commitment to open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

To achieve this, this Strategy is committed to ensuring all data collected or created by AuScope Projects is as open as possible and as closed as necessary, conforms to FAIR, CARE and open science principles, is preserved at full-resolution datasets, and adopts relevant persistent identifiers.

Photo by Jo Condon

Photo by Jarred Cain Lloyd

Above left: Geoscientist Jake Moltzen inspecting HyLogger mineralogy data on screen at the Mineral Resources Tasmania node of the National Virtual Core Library on Palawa / Pakana Country. Above right: geoscientist Dr Kamini Bhowany prepares cables as part of a University of Adelaide led Earth imaging project on Adnyamathanha Country.

“The benefits of open and FAIR data are enormous. Sectors of society worth trillions of dollars use geoscience data for operations, products and services. For example, weather prediction draws on meteorological and other data from around the world. The Global Positioning System depends on real-time observations of solar activity, atmospheric dynamics and Earth's gravity. Earthquake-hazard mitigation and verification of the Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty use seismic data from instruments worldwide.”

— Shelley Stall and co-authors⁵

1. Australian Research Data Commons (2025): <https://bit.ly/43RGifO>
2. Global Indigenous Data Alliance (2021): www.gida-global.org/care
3. AuScope (2020): www.auscope.org.au/strategy
4. UNESCO (2021): <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>
5. Nature Communications (2021): www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-01720-7

Priority 1: Aligned to FAIR, CARE and open science principles

AuScope will strengthen its claim that our research data, data products, and software systems are designed, developed, managed, maintained and used to ensure data, data products and software align with the FAIR, CARE and open science principles.

Above: FAIR and CARE principles go 'hand in hand'.
Image: Global Indigenous Data Alliance

1. AuScope (2025): www.auscope.org.au/earthbank
2. NCI (2025): <https://bit.ly/43TIZPa>
3. AuScope (2025): <https://repository.data.auscope.org.au>
4. AuScope (2025): <https://mate.science>
5. ARDC (2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10656276>
6. GIDA (2025): <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

The current movement toward open data and open science does not fully engage with Indigenous Peoples rights and interests. Existing principles within the open data movement (e.g. FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) primarily focus on characteristics of data that will facilitate increased data sharing among entities while ignoring power differentials and historical contexts. The emphasis on greater data sharing alone creates a tension for Indigenous Peoples who are also asserting greater control over the application and use of Indigenous data and Indigenous Knowledge for collective benefit. This includes the right to create value from Indigenous data in ways that are grounded in Indigenous worldviews and realise opportunities within the knowledge economy.

— Global Indigenous Data Alliance⁶

Context

AuScope has been working towards a capability in FAIR data across all our Projects and recognises that our diverse community of researchers, research infrastructures and representative research domains possess equally diverse FAIR, CARE and open science capabilities and capacities. For example, AuScope and our community have:

- Begun tracking our Project-level capability via FAIR data self-assessment.
- Included FAIR data, minimum metadata and multi-processing level requirements in Participant Agreement contracts.
- Developed the research community-focussed EarthBank¹ (formally AusGeochem) portal.
- Developed the AuScope data collection by partnering with the National Computational Infrastructure NCI through the NCI Data Catalogue² for larger volume and/or computationally intensive datasets.
- Developed the AuScope Data Repository³, dedicated to the preservation and continuous accessibility of geoscientific data generated by Australia's geoscience community.

Implementation

— Under the guiding principles of FAIR, CARE and open science, AuScope will provide for the management, maintenance, and use of:

- Community-identified datasets of national importance to geoscience research in appropriate and curated data repositories and catalogues.
 - Larger volumes and/or computationally intensive data collocated with required compute, e.g. NCI Data Catalogue.
 - Workflows and outputs of geodynamics, geophysics, and multi-physics geoscience simulation, analysis and modelling, e.g. Model Atlas of the Earth (M@TE).⁴
- AuScope-funded data in EarthBank will be managed, maintained, and used in alignment with FAIR data principles.
- AuScope and Geoscience Australia will develop an agreement for the sustainable and long-term preservation and management of geoscience research datasets of national significance and/or continental scale.
- AuScope will operationalise PIDs for instruments, grants, and other entities in alignment with national and international PID research infrastructure strategies, namely the Australian national Persistent Identifier (PID) strategy 2024⁵ developed by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC).
- AuScope will seek to operationalise the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, specific to the Australian context and in alignment with international perspectives.

Priority 2: International best practice and agreed standards

AuScope will strengthen its claim that our research data systems are operated and governed by international best practices and agreed discipline and technical standards. To guarantee that our teams have this capability and capacity, AuScope will allocate resources for development opportunities and collaborate with discipline and technical experts.

Context

AuScope's community includes a diverse range of research data experts in fields such as geophysics, geochemistry, geodynamics, Earth observation, and informatics. AuScope's community also maintains strong connections with international organisations that have significant research data expertise. These organisations include American Geophysical Union (AGU), the British Geological Survey (BGS), CODATA, EarthScope, Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP), the European Geosciences Union (EGU), the European Plate Observing System (EPOS; including Geo-INQUIRE and ChEESE), OneGeochemistry, Research Data Alliance (RDA), and the United States Geological Survey (USGS).

Implementation

- AuScope will support the development of research data capability across all of our Programs and career stages.
- AuScope values and will support long-term collaborations with significant national and international research data experts, organisations, scientific expert bodies (unions, associations, societies), research infrastructures, initiatives and communities.
- AuScope will continue participating in global domain specific research data initiatives, including OneGeochemistry, with the aim of having EarthBank recognised as a curated geochemical database.
- AuScope will support the development and adoption of AI readiness standards and practices for research data, data products, and software.

Building on the essential principles of academic freedom, research integrity and scientific excellence, open science sets a new paradigm that integrates into the scientific enterprise practices for reproducibility, transparency, sharing and collaboration resulting from the increased opening of scientific contents, tools and processes.

— UNESCO¹

1. UNESCO (2022): <https://doi.org/10.54677/UTCD9302>

Priority 3: Collaborative problem solving

AuScope will be recognised internally and externally as a leading geoscience and research data infrastructure capability through active leadership, intentional development and collaborative problem-solving.

Context

AuScope has a strong leadership and collaborative problem-solving history within the Australian and international geoscience and research infrastructure communities. AuScope develops valuable knowledge and essential technical skills by partnering with external experts. As the scale and complexity of research data continue to grow, AuScope must continue to leverage available solutions, support internal and external development of research data capability, and collaborate to solve research data problems.

Implementation

- AuScope will provide leadership and development opportunities in relevant research data capability for community members across all career levels.
- AuScope will support the development of Australia's research data capability through strategic engagement opportunities, e.g. placements, (formal or informal) mentorship and training programs.
- AuScope-funded research data Projects will engage with, learn from, and collaborate with relevant Australian and international expert communities to provide technical and social solutions.

“Since its inception, AuScope has worked in close partnership with the geoscience research community to design, develop and deliver trusted research data systems. Our commitment to openness, interoperability, and long-term sustainability helps shape our national and international communities’ data infrastructure, supporting scientific discovery and real-world impact. I am truly grateful to work with people who are committed to making every day impact for our community now, and into the future.”

— Dr Rebecca Farrington, Director of Research Data Systems

Left: Scientists from around Australia at the Integrated Earth 2023 event on Ngunawal and Ngambri Country. Centre: Dr Simon Hodgson from CODATA speaking at EGU24 in Vienna with AuScope team member, Dr Jens Klump from CSIRO in the foreground. Right: AuScope team and community members including Dr Myra Kemp, Dr Sarah Kachovich, Dr Rebecca Farrington and Dr Sima Mousavi at the 2023 Australian Earth Sciences Convention (AESC) event on Whadjuk Noongar Country.

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